

Kinetics of dissociation of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) in aqueous and reverse micellar media — catalysis of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions

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The rate of dissociation of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) ($[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$) is markedly increased in the presence of metal ions, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} in the water pools of CTAB reverse micelles in chloroform-hexane mixture (3 : 2, v/v) compared to the aqueous medium. In both the media, the $k' - [\text{Metal ion}]_{\text{eff}}$ profiles exhibit limiting behavior at higher metal ion concentrations and the plots of $1/k' \text{ vs } 1/[\text{Metal ion}]_{\text{eff}}$ are linear with positive slopes and intercepts. The kinetic results are in accord with the mechanism envisaging the formation of 1 : 1 binuclear intermediate between $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ and metal ion following the rupture of one of the coordinate bonds of 1,10-phenanthroline aided by the nucleophilic effect of bromide ion. The catalytic effect of the metal ions in both the media is in accordance with the Irving-William series.

The kinetics of dissociations of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)-iron(II) ($\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}$) and tris(2,2'-bipyridyl)iron(II) ($\text{Fe}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$) have been extensively studied in conventional aqueous medium in the presence of acid and in various aqueous organic mixtures¹. Anions like SCN⁻ and Cl⁻ accelerate the aquation in the methanol-water mixtures due to the formation of ions-pairs². The aquation of tris(2,2'-bipyridyl)iron(II) proceeds with considerable rate in the water pools of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) reverse micelles³ in the mixtures of chloroform and hexane (3 : 2, v/v) at pH 6.97 but the reaction is immeasurably slow in conventional aqueous medium at this pH. This has been ascribed to the lower polarity of the water pool, being comparable to aqueous methanol mixtures, conducive for ion-pairing between complex and Br⁻, the latter ion exerting nucleophilic effect. The anions SCN⁻, Cl⁻ have still greater effect on the aquation in this medium.

In addition to the nucleophilic effects of anions, electrophilic effects of metal ions on the complexes are also possible. Kopanica and Stara⁴ reported the ligand exchange reaction between hydrated nickel(II) and copper(II) triethylenetetraminehexaacetate and the reverse reaction, in which binuclear intermediate has been proposed. Metal ions exert Lewis acid effects on complexes weakening the coordinate bond and making them amenable for nucleophilic effect^{5,6}. It is interesting to study these metal ion effects in the reverse micellar media whose water pools have special properties like low polarity. The present authors made an attempt in that direction choosing the dissociation of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) and the results are presented

in this paper.

Results and discussion

The dissociation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ is immeasurably slow in the conventional aqueous medium at pH 6.9. But the reaction proceeds with measurable rate in the presence of CTAB reverse micelle in the chloroform-hexane mixture (3 : 2, v/v). The reaction is free energy-driven⁷ in this medium because 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) has higher solubility in the chloroform-hexane-water mixtures compared to water. The reaction in this medium is markedly catalyzed by Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions. In all these cases, final products are Fe^{II}(aq), M^{II}(aq), and phen. Presumably, even if the complexes of 1,10-phenanthroline with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are formed initially, they undergo dissociation, the ligand finally being solubilized by the non-aqueous pseudo-phase of reverse micelle. The reaction in the presence of CTAB reverse micelles can be considered to take place entirely in the water pool rather than on the micellar surface due to electrostatic repulsion between positively charged micellar surface and $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$.

The kinetic study has been carried out at an overall concentration of CTAB in the range 0.1–0.3 mol dm⁻³ and the volume fraction of the dissolved water (7.44×10^{-3} – 82.12×10^{-3} ml). The counter ion Br⁻ is constrained in the water pools of the reverse micelles and so is the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phen})_3]^{2+}$. It is known that the dielectric constants of water pools of the reverse micelles of CTAB are near to that of the methanol-water mixtures⁸.

The occurrence of the reaction in the reverse micellar

system must be due to the nucleophilic effect of bromide ion aiding the disruption of the metal-ligand bond. In these low dielectric constant conditions, extensive ion-pair formation between $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ and Br^- is possible. The effective Br^- concentration (overall concentration of CTAB/volume fraction of water) ranges between 20.0 and 3.33 mol dm^{-3} when the molar ratio W changes from 1.39 to 16.6 and hence it is likely that all $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ complex is present in the form of ion-pairs $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}, \text{Br}^-$. To ascertain this, the authors studied the effect of $[\text{Br}^-]$ on rate in this concentration and noticed no appreciable effect of bromide ion on the rate of dissociation of the complex, supporting the view that almost all the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ is in the form of the ion-pair $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}, \text{Br}^-$. The authors also found that the rate of dissociation of the complex in the medium is not influenced by change in the overall concentration of CTAB at constant molar ratio W . Under these conditions, the increase in the overall concentration of CTAB results in the increase of the micellar interface. Lack of any effect of the concentration of CTAB on rate shows that the reactant is not bound at the interface and also the CTAB molecules present on the interface does not have any catalytic or inhibitory effect on the reaction. The reaction, thus, entirely takes place in the water pool. The author has observed an appreciable decrease in rate with increasing W at constant $[\text{CTAB}]$, presumably due to the attenuation of special properties of the water pool. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k') are included in Table 1.

Table 1. Rate constants for the dissociation of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) in the water pools of CTAB-chloroform-hexane reverse micelles

$[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+} = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$
 $10^5 \times k' (\text{s}^{-1})$

W	$[\text{CTAB}]_0 = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{CTAB}]_0 = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{CTAB}]_0 = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$
1.39	4.92	4.87	4.77
2.77	2.77	3.01	2.94
4.16	2.13	2.11	2.07
6.94	1.82	1.75	1.77
12.5	1.10	1.25	1.15

The results in Table 2 for the dissociation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ in the CTAB reverse micelles show that in the presence of the metal ions Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} , the pseudo-first order rate constants show tendency of limiting behavior at high $[\text{Metal ion}]$, indicating the formation of an intermediate 1 : 1 adduct between metal ion and $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$. The intermediate is between $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ and the metal ion, where one of the coordinate bonds of the complex

Table 2. Rate constants for the dissociation of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) in the water pools of CTAB-chloroform-hexane reverse micelles in the presence of metal ions

$[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CTAB}] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Metal ion	Volume fraction $10^3 \times f$	W	$[\text{Br}^-] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^2 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^3 \times k' \text{ s}^{-1}$	$10^{-2} K'_2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$	$10^4 \times k \text{ s}^{-1}$
Ni^{II}	4.97	2.77	20.0	2.00	2.77	0.652	47.6
				4.00	3.52		
				10.00	4.21		
				12.50	4.32		
				25.00	4.60		
	7.44	4.16	13.3	2.66	2.12	1.40	25.0
				5.33	2.40		
				10.00	2.53		
				16.60	2.59		
				13.30	2.63		
	12.30	6.94	8.0	1.14	1.62	1.83	22.4
				1.71	1.70		
				2.81	1.87		
				4.28	1.99		
				5.71	2.05		
22.00	12.5	4.4	0.88	1.28	1.85	19.2	
			1.33	1.47			
			2.22	1.62			
			4.44	1.77			
			5.55	1.80			
Co^{II}	7.44	4.16	13.3	2.50	1.53	1.22	19.2
				3.33	1.57		
				8.30	1.79		
				16.60	1.85		
				25.00	1.89		
Cu^{II}	7.44	4.16	13.33	2.50	2.37	1.42	30.3
				3.33	2.54		
				8.30	2.77		
				16.60	2.89		
				25.00	2.98		
				33.30	3.03		

$[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ is severed (under the nucleophilic effect of bromide ion), the freed nitrogen forming a coordinate bond

with the metal ion. The metal ion now influences the further severing of the iron(II)-1,10-phenanthroline bonds.

The dissociation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ in the water pools of CTAB reverse micelles in the presence of metal ions, should involve not only the ion-pairing between $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ and Br^- but also between metal ion and Br^- , because of the low dielectric constant condition and high concentration of the bromide ion in the water pools. According to Tachiyashiki and Yamatara², the formation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ and phen from $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ is rate-determining and further dissociation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ to $\text{Fe}^{2+}(\text{aq})$ and phen is fast. On this basis the rate-determining stages can be represented as

Using the equilibrium treatment described by Laidler⁹ it can be shown that

$$[\text{X}_2] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}, \text{Br}^-] [\text{M}^{2+}]}{1 + K_1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{M}^{2+}]} \quad (5)$$

where, $[\text{M}^{2+}]$ is the free metal ion concentration in water pool. The concentration of the ion-pair between metal ion and Br^- , (MBr^+) is given by the equation,

$$[\text{MBr}^+] = \frac{K_3 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}} \quad (6)$$

Hence the free metal ion concentration in the water pool is given as

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{M}^{2+}] &= [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} - [\text{MBr}^+] \\ &= [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} - \frac{K_3 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}} \\ &= \frac{[\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}} \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$[\text{X}_2] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}, \text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}} \left\{ \frac{[\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}} \right\}}{1 + K_1 + \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k K_2 K_1 [\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}, \text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}} \left\{ \frac{[\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}} \right\}}{1 + K_1 + \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}}{1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}}} \quad (8)$$

and the pseudo-first order rate constant (k') under the conditions, $[\text{M}] \gg [\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}]$ is given as

$$k' = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} / (1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}})}{1 + K_1 + (K_1 K_2 [\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}} / (1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}}))} \quad (9)$$

According to eqn. (9), plots of k' vs $[\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}$ should exhibit limiting behavior at high metal ion concentrations. Further, plots of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{M}^{2+}]_{\text{eff}}$ should be linear with positive

slopes $\left(\frac{1 + K_1}{k K_1 K_2 / (1 + K_3 [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}})} \right)$ and positive intercept

($1/k$). Such plots have been obtained in the catalysis by each of the metal ions studied ($\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Co^{II}). The change in the surfactant concentration at constant W has no effect on k' . With increasing $[\text{Surfactant}]$, at constant W , the micellar surface increases, the bromide ion concentration being constant. The insensitivity of k' to increase in micellar surface shows that the dissociation reaction does not take place on the micellar surface but takes place entirely in the water pool. At constant $[\text{Surfactant}]$, the increase in W results in increase in dielectric constant and this should result in decrease in rate constant (k) since the reaction involves the formation of less polar product, phen, and according to Laidler such a reaction should proceed with decreased rate with increasing dielectric constant⁹. The metal ion acceleration of the dissociation is due to its Lewis acid behavior which will lower the basic properties of coordinated groups, and so enhance their disruption by nucleophiles⁵. The Lewis acid effect is according to Irving-Williams series¹⁰: $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. At constant W (Table 2) (constant $[\text{Br}^-]$ and constant properties of water pool), k is also in the same order for the metal ion acceleration. However, a quantitative kinetic analysis of these changes cannot be carried out due to the fact that as W changes, the dielectric constant of the water pool changes and so does K_3 . The

value of K'_2 ($= K_1K_2/(1 + K_1)/(1 + K_3[\text{Br}^-]_{\text{eff}})$) obtained from the values of intercept and slope of eqn. (9) at constant W also conforms to Irving-Williams series (Table 2). The increase in K'_2 with increase in W can be traced to simultaneous decrease in $[\text{Br}^-]$. The results in Table 2 also show that decrease in k with increase in W is more pronounced at lower W values (2.77–4.16) than that at higher W 's. At lower W 's the special properties of the water pool like lower dielectric constant, are more pronounced¹¹ than at higher W 's.

Kinetics in conventional aqueous medium :

The metal ion catalysis has also been observed in the aqueous medium but the catalysis is ten times less than in the water pools of the CTAB reverse micelles. The greater catalysis in the latter medium is due to the nucleophilic effect of bromide ion in this medium and possibility of ion-pair between $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ and Br^- at lower polarity conditions. The kinetic pattern in the aqueous medium is identical to that observed in the water pools of reverse micelles. The k' vs $[\text{M}]$ plots show limiting behavior at higher $[\text{M}]$, and plots of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{M}]$ are linear with positive slopes and intercepts. There is no bromide ion and also the high dielectric constant does not permit any stable ion-pairing. The rate-determining stages can be expressed as

The product in this medium is the corresponding metal ion complex with 1,10-phenanthroline. The rate law for this mechanism is given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_4K_5[\text{M}^{2+}][\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}]}{1 + K_4 + K_4K_5[\text{M}^{2+}]} \quad (12)$$

under the conditions, $[\text{M}^{2+}] \gg [\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}]$

$$\text{and } k' = \frac{KK_4K_5[\text{M}^{2+}]}{(1 + K_4 + K_4K_5[\text{M}^{2+}])}$$

Accordingly, linear plots with positive intercepts have been obtained between $1/k'$ and $1/[\text{M}^{2+}]$. The value of k , K'_4 ($= K_4K_5/(1 + K_4)$) calculated from intercept and slopes of these plots are presented in Table 3. It is seen that the variation of k with the metal ion is according to Irving-William series of Lewis acid effect. The higher value of K_2 in aqueous me-

Table 3. Rate constants for the dissociation of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) in the aqueous medium in the present of metal ions

Metal ion	$10^3 [\text{M}^{\text{II}}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k'$ s ⁻¹	$10^{-3} K'_4$	$10^4 k$
Co ^{II}	1.45	1.56	1.09	2.38
	2.18	1.77		
	2.91	1.81		
	3.64	2.04		
	5.82	2.21		
Ni ^{II}	1.45	1.73	1.15	2.94
	2.18	1.98		
	2.91	2.08		
	3.64	2.27		
	5.82	2.40		
Cu ^{II}	1.45	2.01	1.17	3.07
	2.18	2.37		
	2.91	2.40		
	3.64	2.66		
	5.82	2.81		

dium than that in reverse micellar medium (K'_2) is due to absence of Br^- ions in the aqueous medium.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. All chemicals used were of A.R grade. Hexane and chloroform were distilled before use. A 0.02 mol dm⁻³ solution of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) was prepared by mixing stoichiometric amounts of ferrous ammonium sulfate and 1,10-phenanthroline in water. The pH of 4.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ solution of the above complex was found to be 6.97. The solutions of 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sulfate salts of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} were prepared and standardized using the literature methods. The sulfate ion did not have any effect on the rate of reaction in the aqueous as well as in the reverse micellar media.

Preparation of reverse micellar system and initiation of the reaction : In a typical experiment, CTAB solution was dissolved in a chloroform-hexane mixture (3 : 2, v/v) to obtain a concentration of 0.1 mol dm⁻³. Small quantity of the aqueous solution of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} or Cu^{II} (0.025–0.3 cm³) was injected in CTAB solution (10 cm³). The tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) complex was then added to initiate the reaction. The mixture was shaken sufficiently to obtain a transparent and homogeneous solution that can be regarded as a reverse micellar system¹². In all the experiments, the molar ratio of $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]/[\text{CTAB}] (=W)$ was varied in the range

2.77–12.5. The reaction was monitored by measuring the absorbance of the complex at 510 nm under the conditions $[\text{Metal ion}] \gg [\text{Fe(phen)}_3^{2+}]$ ($\epsilon_{510} = 11000 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) using Milton-Roy (Spectronic 1201) spectrophotometer with thermostated cell compartment. The kinetic data are the averages from triplicate runs with reproducibility of $\pm 5\%$.

Product in aqueous medium : A $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution of $[\text{Fe(phen)}_3^{2+}]$ was mixed with equivalent amount of metal ions (Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II}). After completion of the reaction (indicated by discharge of orange colour), the spectrum of the product was scanned and compared with authentic samples of 1,10-phenanthroline, metal-1,10-phenanthroline complex and metal ions of the same concentration. The spectrum was found to overlap with that of metal-1,10-phenanthroline complexes obtained by direct mixing ($\epsilon_{430} = 110 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $[\text{Co(phen)}_3]^{2+}$, $\epsilon_{20} = 13 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $[\text{Ni(phen)}_3]^{2+}$ and $\epsilon_{680} = 60 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for the Cu^{II} complex¹³). The latter is known to exist in five-coordinate form of 1,10-phenanthroline complex of Cu^{II} ¹⁴.

Product in reverse-micellar medium : In the UV region, the product spectrum was identical with that of 1,10-phenanthroline. In the visible region, there is no absorbance at wavelengths corresponding to the metal ion-1,10-phenanthroline complex.

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